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A STUDY TO EXAMINE SELF-EFFICACY, SELF-REGULATION AND
THEIR RELATIONSHIP TO OVERWEIGHT PATIENTS WHO
UTILIZE A HEALTH COACH

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

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By

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study was to examine whether there was a positive effect on overweight individuals who utilized an exercise coach. It also explored the relationships of self-efficacy (SE) and self-regulation (SR) to exercise adherence in normal-weight and overweight individuals. A comparative descriptive design was used to study adult patients in a family practice clinic who were selected by convenience sampling during a routine visit. At that time, participants completed surveys that measured levels of general SE and exercise SR along with a demographic questionnaire. Tools utilized were the General Self-Efficacy Scale, the Self-Regulation Questionnaire for Exercise, and a self-report demographic questionnaire.

Statistical analysis was completed to determine whether there was a positive effect on exercise adherence in overweight individuals who utilized an exercise coach. In addition, statistical interpretations were used to determine whether there was a relationship between SE, SR, and exercise adherence in normal-weight and overweight individuals.

The results indicated a significant relationship between SR and exercise adherence but no significant relationship between SE and exercise adherence. Due to sample size, the study was unable to determine whether there was a positive effect on exercise adherence in overweight individuals who utilized an exercise coach

In conclusion, those who had high levels of exercise adherence were high self-regulators but did not necessarily have high levels of general SE. The study was unable to determine whether there was a positive effect on overweight individuals who used an exercise coach.

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DEDICATION

This project is dedicated to my husband John, and my son Kirk, who supported me with love, patience, and humor throughout the completion of this project. It is also dedicated to my father, Richard McCall, who at 91 years of age continues to amaze me with his inquisitive mind and thirst for new knowledge; and to my mother, Naomi McCall (1921–2002), who was a guiding influence throughout my life and truly valued the importance of healthy habits that she instilled in her children at an early age.

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INTRODUCTION

On a typical street in urban America, a least six out of 10 individuals are considered overweight or obese (National Institute of Health [NIH], National Institute of Diabetes and Digestive and Kidney Diseases [NIDDK], Weight-Control Information Network [WIN], 2013). This is a serious and increasing complex problem. Obesity is a chronic condition that contributes to acute and chronic disease which results in hospitalization and readmission as well as complications when treating illnesses (Ogden, Carroll, Kit, & Flegal, 2012; Pearson, Irwin, Morrow, & Hall, 2012). The increasing prevalence of obesity in the United States is associated with significant health consequences. Most recently, obesity has been associated with complications related to influenza. As of January 2014, 43% of all people hospitalized with influenza across the United States were considered obese (Centers for Disease Control [CDC], 2014).

It is well known that increasing physical activity has a positive outcome on obesity, cardiovascular disease, stroke, hypertension, type 2 diabetes mellitus, osteoporosis, colon cancer, breast cancer, anxiety and depression (Haskell et al., 2007; Pearson et al., 2012). However, only a fifth of adults participate in a level of exercise or physical activity which is sufficient enough to lead to these known health benefits (Barnes & Schoenberg, 2012; Lee, Arthur, & Avis, 2008). According to the World Health Organization (WHO; 2013) at least 400 million adults were obese in 2005 and at that time that level was projected to rise to 700 million by 2012. Exercise is one factor that can have an impact on reducing the prevalence of obesity. Nonetheless, motivation to exercise is a major problem. Many individuals struggling with obesity and the lifelong behaviors associated with it cannot motivate themselves to exercise (Schelling

et al., 2009; West et al., 2011; Wilson, Mack, & Grattan, 2008). In the United States, approximately half of adults starting an exercise program will discontinue participation within 6 months (Rodgers, Hall, Duncan, Pearson, & Milne, 2010; Wilson, Sabiston, Mack, & Blanchard, 2012). Low motivation, past negative learning experiences with exercise, self-efficacy (SE), time barriers, and the high cost of training programs are all factors that impede physical activity in adults (Mceachan, Sutton, & Myers, 2010; Schelling et al., 2009; Wilson et al., 2012), yet a certain set of individuals are able to follow a regular regime of exercise. What is it that sets them apart from their counterparts, and can these factors be applied to those who do not exercise in order to change behaviors?

It has been found that regular exercisers are well established with more self-determined regulations, both intrinsic and identified (Rodgers et al., 2010). Successful adherence to maintaining an exercise regime on a long-term basis is difficult, and to be successful often requires the self-regulation (SR) of one's behavior by overruling a learned behavior (e.g., sitting on the couch watching television) and exchanging it with a less characteristic but more beneficial behavior (e.g., going for a bike ride or taking a walk) (McAuley et al., 2011). How do behaviors of those who exercise develop and persist? Utilizing a paid sports or physical trainer to motivate a nonexerciser is often effective but can be expensive. Attending a group class with a motivational leader can also be effective, but many obese patients choose not to participate in group or individual exercise at a gym or community center due to embarrassment related to body size (Schelling et al., 2009). Lifelong behavioral habits may be difficult to overcome without encouragement and education on a regular, frequent basis. Life style coaching

as an intervention for obesity has been associated with clinically significant increases in participants' self-esteem and their mental, physical, and overall health status (DiLillo, Siegfried, & West, 2003; Newnham-Kanas, Irwin, & Morrow, 2008; Newnham-Kanas, Irwin, Morrow, & Battram, 2011; Wadden et al., 2007).

The Patient Protection and Affordable Care Act (PPACA) of 2010 offers opportunities for motivating healthcare organizations to implement programs that could potentially reduce costs and improve quality of care while modernizing care and improving access to care (Duncan, Beatty, & Day, 2011; Lanese, Dey, Srivastava, & Figler, 2011b). Indeed, patient coaches have already been found to be quite effective as an adjunct to treatment in chronic diseases such as diabetes, congestive heart failure (CHF), and chronic obstructive lung disease (COPD; Kilgore, 2010; Shaw et al., 2012). These successful programs may lead to an opportunity to implement the patient coach in different areas of patient care. In particular, use of a patient coach for encouraging adherence to exercise could be a means to prevent unnecessary hospitalization and readmission and decrease progression of obesity and its effects on quality of life.

Background of the Problem

Motivating people to sustain participation in physical activity has been a crucial point of research in exercise psychology (Wilson et al., 2012). Health studies of populations consistently link lower levels of physical activity to physical (hypertension) and psychological (depression) problems that greatly affect the quality of life and shorten the length of life (Haskell et al., 2007). As discussed, about 50% of adults who start an exercise program discontinue the program within 6 months (Wilson et al., 2012). Losing weight can be accomplished through intake of less calories and/or output

of more calories (S. R. Williams, 1994). Committing to regular physical exercise as a lifelong commitment is not an easy task for many people.

It is well known that coaching self-determination in sports, business, and psychology has resulted in successful outcomes in motivating people to obtain goals (Gagne & Deci, 2005). Nurses are already involved with coaching in many different aspects of patient care such as adherence to diet for diabetics and monitoring of symptoms for patients with heart failure and COPD (Hayes, McCahon, Panahi, Hamre, & Pohlman, 2008). Coaching in the advanced practice nurse (APN)–patient relationship is compatible with the professional ideals of the APN. Successful patient coaching for behavior change involves helping clients consider options, make choices and plans, and identify challenges to change (Hayes & Kalmakis, 2007; Newnham-Kanas et al., 2008).

APNs in practice are already teaching and coaching patients on different aspects of self-care, including diet and medication adherence. It would be quite natural for an APN to evolve into a patient coach in order to motivate patients to adhere to an exercise program and to lead other healthcare workers in a healthcare coach role. Readiness of patients to accept coaching from a healthcare coach should be determined. Patients often need regular one-on-one encouragement to continue with self-care in the early stages, during which self-determination is a significant part in the changing of behaviors and emotional attachments that have been firmly ingrained for many years. It is not cost effective or practical to bring patients into the clinical setting frequently enough to enforce these changes. Regular, frequent coaching sessions outside of the clinical setting, such as by telephone calls or through text messaging and email, would be an

alternative. These can be economical, practical, and have the potential to succeed in helping patients to achieve goals such as adhering to regular physical activity.

Statement of the Problem

Obesity is a prevalent problem in the United States and is a leading cause of chronic conditions such as cardiac disease, stroke, Type 2 diabetes, and certain types of cancer. Exercise has been found to be an effective method of reducing weight. However, staying motivated to adhere to a regular exercise program is a problem for many people, including obese individuals. It is necessary to determine a cost-effective method for motivating obese adults to adhere to regular physical exercise.

In the primary care setting, AP nurses are frequently asked by obese or overweight patients for assistance in losing and maintaining weight loss. It is impractical to commit to coaching and encouraging these patients in the clinical setting on a frequent enough basis to engender self-determined regulations and effect sufficient change. Coaches have utilized self-determination concepts in business, sports, recovery from injury, and psychology effectively in the past. Healthcare coaches have been utilized effectively with positive outcomes for other chronic diseases and conditions. Applying a healthcare coach in a self-determination model to encourage adherence to exercises in obese patients could be an economical and reasonable alternative.

Statement of Purpose

The purpose of this study was to examine whether there was a positive effect on overweight individuals who utilized an exercise coach. The secondary purpose was to explore the relationship of SE and SE in exercise adherence.

Significance of the Study

More than two thirds (68.8%) of adults in the United States are considered to be overweight or obese (NIH, NIDDK, WIN, 2013; Ogden et al., 2012). Obesity causes and complicates chronic conditions that are some of the leading causes of death (NIH, NIDDK, WIN, 2013). Obesity is associated with psychological and social impairment that directly impacts total health care costs and burdens of the disease globally (Newnham-Kanas et al., 2008; Schelling et al., 2009).

According to the Ogden et al. (2012), in the United States, non-Hispanic Blacks have the highest age-adjusted rates of obesity (49.5%), followed by Mexican Americans (40.4%), all Hispanics (39.1%), and non-Hispanic Whites (34.3%). Obesity prevalence varies across states and regions. In 2012 the CDC reported the South as having the highest prevalence of obesity (i.e., 34.9% in Mississippi) and the West as having the lowest (i.e., 20.7% in Colorado).

Obesity in adults was defined as a Body Mass Index (BMI) greater than or equal to 30, and overweight is defined as a BMI of 25 to 29. The prevalence of obesity in the United States has increased during the last decades of the 20th century and has resulted in increases in chronic health conditions such as hypertension, stroke, hyperlipidemia, Type 2 diabetes, and certain types of cancer (Ogden et al., 2012). Medical costs associated with obesity in 2008 were estimated at \$147 billion. In addition, active individuals use health-care services to a lesser extent than those that are sedentary (Ashworth, Chad, Harrison, Reeder, & Marshall, 2005; Ogden et al., 2012). In 2009–2010, almost 41 million women and approximately 37 million men were considered obese in the United States; however, between 1999 and 2000 and between 2009 and

2010, the prevalence of obesity increased among men but did not increase among women (Ogden et al., 2012). According to Finkelstein, Fiebelkorn, and Wang (2004), the healthcare costs directly related to obesity in the United States were estimated to be \$75 billion in 2003 dollars, with about half of this amount being financed by Medicare and Medicaid. At the state-level, estimates ranged from \$87 million in Wyoming to \$1.7 billion in California.

In developed countries physical inactivity is a leading cause of preventable death and morbidity. Regular physical activity is a potentially effective treatment for various medical conditions including osteoporosis, cardiovascular disease and depression (Ashworth et al., 2005). Even though exercise promotes weight loss, which can improve medical conditions, over half of the people in the United States did not report exercising on a regular basis, although 1 in 3 adults who had seen a physician or other healthcare provider in the past 12 months had been advised to begin or to continue to do exercise or physical activity (Barnes & Schoenborn, 2012). It should be noted that advising a patient to exercise without a clear-cut plan and frequent follow-up has not been a successful strategy. Developing the behaviors necessary to follow and maintain a regular exercise program is a complex process that can often not be achieved on one's own.

The significance of this study was to determine whether the use of a healthcare coach would be an effective method for helping obese and overweight individuals adhere to an exercise program. The second part would be determining whether there was a relationship with overweight individuals who did not exercise and levels of SE and SE.

Summary

Americans continue to struggle with obesity despite more knowledge and better access to modern methods to change. The effects of obesity on acute illness and other chronic conditions are well documented and are a great burden on the healthcare system. Exercise is known to be an effective means to lose weight, improve overall health, and maintain weight loss and better health. Motivation to exercise and adherence to an exercise program are needed to stimulate change in self-care behaviors of individuals, thereby promoting positive beliefs and a beneficial outcome for the population as a whole.

The healthcare coach has already been shown to be effective and financially beneficial in controlling and monitoring other chronic conditions and diseases. Use of a healthcare coach to motivate overweight and obese individuals to adhere to an exercise program may be an effective intervention in the complex treatment of obesity. Both high SE and the ability to self-regulate have been found to be predictors of adherence to treatment for diabetes, COPD, and CHF. Adherence has been accomplished through boosting SE and emphasizing SE in these challenging patients. With obesity now being one of the leading causes of health problems and poor outcomes when associated with the treatment of other chronic and acute illnesses, focusing on reducing obesity through regular exercise will lead to improved overall wellness both physically and mentally and better outcomes in the treatment of other diseases.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Motivational Interviewing and Coaching

Lifestyle modification has been found to be an important aspect in inducing clinically significant weight loss. There are several factors that contribute to these changes; one in particular is continued patient–practitioner contact either in person or by electronic communication (Wadden et al., 2007). One study evaluated the effect of using motivational interviewing (MI) in co-active life coaching (CALC) as an intervention for adults struggling with obesity (Newnham-Kanas et al., 2008). This pilot study used weekly coaching session over the phone that took place in the participant’s choice of setting (usually participant’s own home) except for the first session, which was face- to-face with the lead researcher. Significant changes were observed in self-esteem, SE, physical activity, and nutrition, along with decreases in waist circumference and weight. MI using CALC was found to be effective in helping participants with weight loss and exercise adherence (Newnham-Kanas et al., 2011).

Another study compared the effectiveness of MI via CALC) to the Lifestyle, Exercise, Attitudes, Relationships, Nutrition (LEARN) Program for Weight Management, a well validated and thoroughly tested educational/ cognitive behavior program for self-esteem and quality of life in changing behaviors of obese individuals. The study’s results showed that MI via CALC compared favorably with LEARN as an obesity treatment and that both treatments could be offered based on individual learning styles and preferences with the expectation of equivalent outcomes (Pearson et al., 2012).

In a descriptive study that reviewed six longitudinal studies, each of the four types of motivational regulation utilized by regular exercisers was assessed to determine the differences in SE between regular exercisers and beginning exercisers (Rodgers et al., 2010). The four types of motivational regulation identified in this study were external, interjected, identified, and intrinsic. The researchers determined that there was a significant difference in self-determination between regular exercisers and initiates. This difference was noted even after initiates had been exercising for 6 months when identified, and intrinsic motivation remained low with the initiates. The study noted that some people do not find exercise to be intrinsically enjoyable and that identified motivation had the strongest correlation with exercise adherence (Rodgers et al., 2010).

Reducing exercise program dropouts were investigated in a randomized experimental, controlled study that compared standardized motivational intervention with nonspecific control intervention in an 8-week exercise program with obese individuals. The nonspecific control group utilized a relaxation intervention. It was found that the motivational intervention group had fewer dropouts and a higher than the relaxation intervention group. The study showed that motivational interventions are effective in reducing high dropout rates in physical activity programs and suggested that this simple intervention could be improved with more sessions and longer periods of exercise (Schelling et al., 2009).

One of the primary goals of the PPACA is to improve healthcare quality while reducing costs (U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, 2014). A majority of researchers have found that the most important objective when developing effective and efficient patient-centered medical homes is treatment of people with chronic conditions

at the primary practice setting (Lanese, Srivastava, & Figler, 2011a). In an average primary care practice with a panel of 2,500 patients, a study showed that approximately 21.7 hours per working day are required to meet the needs of patients with chronic and acute complaints as well to provide preventive care (Lanese et al., 2011a). The patient coach function could be a solution for prevention and managing of chronic conditions with personalized treatment plans that would include psychosocial variables, patient's readiness for change, and patient preferences. This study identified the financial and clinical benefits of adding a health coach to a primary care practice to achieve these goals and free up nurse practitioners and physicians to provide other care for their patient population. (Lanese et al., 2011a). Because healthcare coaching programs are relatively new, there is a need for increased published research on the effectiveness of health coaching to show that healthcare providers are achieving outcomes that are related to use of the healthcare coach.

In Part 2 of patient coach research of Lanese, Srivastava, and Figler (2011b), the pilot study dealt with the financial impact of hiring a healthcare coach in an eight-physician office setting. This study reviewed data from diabetic laboratory tests and data regarding diabetic visits and noted improvements in both the lab tests and the frequency of visits of these patients. This study showed that a health coach does have the potential for improving health and for saving costs. From a monetary point of view, positive payback was seen in about 3 years. However, decrease in hospitalization was noted sooner and was shown not only to benefit the practice from a financial standpoint but also to benefit to patients' health (Lanese et al., 2011b). Although the study focused

specifically on diabetes, it could imply benefits for other chronic health conditions, such as obesity.

Exercise Adherence

It is much easier to initiate an exercise program than to maintain the behaviors needed to continue with a program (Mullen et al., 2013). Some individuals can sustain an exercise program and to integrate fitness into their daily lives; however, the majority are unable to overcome the obstacles that are associated with sustaining this behavior. In fact, statistics have shown that there is an approximate 50% attrition rate within the first 3–6 months of beginning an exercise regime (Mullen et al., 2013). Some of the strategies utilized to increase adherence have included accentuating program benefits, increasing incentives, decreasing participant burden, maintaining strong tracking programs, frequent contact with participants, and increasing social support (Coday et al., 2005).

Self-Efficacy and Self-Regulation

Albert Bandura developed the concept of SE as a portion of the larger social learning theory that evolved into the social cognitive theory (Ashford & LeCroy, 2010). Social cognitive theory encompasses four interrelated processes—self-observation, self-evaluation, self-reaction and SE—each of which has an effect on reaching goals (Bandura, 1997). SE, or one's belief in the likelihood of completing a goal, is motivating on its own (Lentz, 2002). As a result, individuals are more likely to participate in activities in which they have high SE and are less likely to engage in those in which they do not.

Bandura (1977) identified four sources of information from which one forms beliefs in levels of SE: performance outcomes (past experiences), physiologic feedback (emotional status), vicarious experiences (modeling by others), and verbal persuasion (coaching and feedback; see Figure 1). The exercise healthcare coach focuses on verbal persuasion in order to influence an individual's behavior. Verbal coaching is easy to do and can be done in a variety of ways.

Figure 1. Self-efficacy sources of information. Taken from “Self-Efficacy: Toward a Unifying Theory of Behavioral Change,” by A. Bandura, 1977, *Psychological Review*, 84, retrieved from <https://wikispaces.psu.edu>

SE indicates self-confidence. and people with high SE are more likely to participate in certain behaviors when they believe that they are capable of executing those behaviors successfully (Bandura, 1997). Bandura (1977) described self-regulation as when an individual chooses actions based on what behaviors he or she feels are appropriate or inappropriate.

Relationship of the Study to the Current State of Research

Currently there is a great deal of research on utilizing a healthcare coach to improve outcomes in individuals with chronic conditions such as Type 2 diabetes, CHF, COPD, and other chronic disease states. There is also much research on the value of coaching to improve sports performance and to increase adherence to physical exercise programs. There is very little research on utilizing a health coach with overweight or obese patients to improve adherence to exercise programs. However, at the April 2013 meeting of the National Organization of Nurse Practitioners in Pittsburgh, Pennsylvania, a presentation was made that discussed utilizing the APN as a health and wellness coach and included healthcare coaching to encourage exercise in obese and overweight patients. This presentation was an indication of the movement toward utilizing health coaches for treatment of obesity. In 2013, obesity was formally classified as a chronic medical condition that leads to physical and financial burdens on both the obese individual and the system (Flegal, Kit, & Graubard, 2013). In addition, specialists in pain management are researching the effects of obesity on increased pain and have begun to investigate how to change behaviors in obese individuals to help with decreased weight and better pain management. The relationship between pain and obesity is more than just mechanical overload. Emerging evidence implies that systemic inflammation present in obese individuals also contributes to increased pain and decreased ability to manage pain (Bonakdar, Christo, & Clark, 2013). This suggests that pain can be reduced, along with related comorbidities, by even a modest weight loss and resultant improved fitness.

Statement of the Theoretical Framework

SE theory is a commonly applied theory employed to understand health behavior and encourage behavioral modification. The theory refers to a person's sense of confidence in his or ability to perform certain behaviors in different circumstances. An essential part of SE is that the stronger the belief or confidence is in a certain behavior, the more likely a person is to initiate and continue that behavior (Lee et al., 2008).

SE theory concentrates on the interrelationships among SE, outcome expectancies, and behavior and is a piece of social cognitive theory (Ashford, Edmunds, & French, 2010; D. M. Williams, 2010). SE has been defined as "the belief in one's capabilities to organize and execute the courses of action required to produce given attainments" (Bandura, 1997, p. 46). The central principle of expectancy theories is the weighting of perceived consequences of an action that occurs when most people consider what they stand to gain or lose from performing a behavior. It is this belief in being capable of performing a behavior rather than a willingness to perform a behavior that distinguishes SE from intention theories (Bandura, 1997; D. M. Williams, 2010).

Introduction of the Theoretical Framework

SE theory is derived from four sources: mastery experiences, modeling, verbal persuasion, and physiological and affective states at the time that the SE is evaluated. Mastery experiences are previous successful behavioral performance; modeling is the observation of successful behavior performance (D. M. Williams, 2010; S. L. Williams & French, 2011). According to Bandura (1997), SE is directly related to perceived capability as opposed to actual capability (also see Lee et al., 2008). An example of this would be a person's SE to resist eating ice cream as opposed to SE to calculate a

complex geometry problem (D. M. Williams, 2010). Bandura (1997) based the concept of behavior change on two chief theories: SE and outcome expectations (also see Lee et al., 2008; D. M. Williams, 2010). These two chief theories are not always consistent. For instance, a person may know that there will be positive health benefits to exercising (outcome expectations) but may not believe that he or she is capable of exercising on a daily basis (SE) based on assessment of time available in his or her daily life (Lee et al., 2008).

SE involves the capacity to change and overrule undesirable behaviors or responses (Oaten & Cheng, 2006). Instigating SE can be difficult, as the individual must decide what behavior is or is not appropriate and then choose to act accordingly. Those who find it easier to self-regulate have self-confidence in implementing behaviors, or high levels of SE.

Application of the Theoretical Framework

The belief in one's capabilities to organize and execute certain behaviors or actions to achieve expected outcomes is the core of the SE theory and has often been shown to be a predictor of initiation and adherence to physical activity in adults (Bandura, 1997; S. L. Williams & French, 2011). According to Bandura (1986, 1997), one of the most consistent determinants of many health behaviors is self-efficacy. Increasing SE levels in adults who are not good self-regulators could increase their self-confidence and adherence to exercise. Using a healthcare coach to remind nonexercisers of past positive experiences and instill the belief that they are capable of regular exercise can lead to higher levels of SE and therefore better SE. This procedure has proven to be true in improving the ability to self-regulate and adhere to medical

regimes in patients with COPD and Type 2 diabetes (Lanese et al., 2011b). Research has indicated that self-regulation is directed by a resource that allows people to control impulses and desires (Oaten & Cheng, 2006). The social cognitive theory (SCT), from which the self-efficacy theory was developed, suggests that behavior change develops from changes in motivation and self-regulation (McAuley et al., 2011). Both cognitive and motivational elements that are integrated into the SCT are involved in self-regulatory strategies, such as planning, scheduling, and self-monitoring (Bandura, 1986, 1997). Improving and exerting self-regulation in poor self-regulators theoretically could be done through reinforcement of self-regulatory behaviors by boosting self-efficacy.

METHODOLOGY

This chapter includes information about the design of the study, research question, operational definitions, limitations, and assumptions of the study. The study setting and inclusion–exclusion criteria for the participant sample are identified. Independent, dependent, and extraneous variables are described. In addition, the chapter includes a description of instruments used in the study, procedures for collection of data, protection of human participants, and statistical analysis procedure of data collected.

Research Questions

The primary research question in this study was, “Is there a positive effect on exercise adherence in overweight individuals who utilize an exercise coach?” The secondary research question had two parts:

1. Is there a relationship between SE and exercise adherence in overweight and normal-weight individuals who exercise?
2. Is there a relationship between SE and exercise adherence in overweight and normal-weight individuals who exercise?

Research Design

A comparative descriptive design was used to study the relationships of exercise adherence, SE, and SE in obese and normal-weight patients who exercised with and without an exercise coach. Gender, age, marital status, and ethnicity were also considered. Information was collected through self-administered questionnaires. Data collection has to be reasonable, practical, and suitable for the population of interest as well as the clinical setting in order to be the appropriate method for a research study (Moran, Burson, & Conrad, 2014). Use of self-report, written questionnaires was

appropriate for this convenience sample of adults who were able to speak, read, and write English.

Operational Definitions

The following terms were operationally defined for use in this study:

Exercise Adherence

For the purpose of this study, exercise adherence is defined as participation in 20 minutes of exercise 3 or more days a week.

Exercise Coach

An exercise coach is a group exercise class leader, private exercise trainer, health coach, or sports coach.

Overweight

A Body Mass Index (BMI) of 25 or greater is overweight. BMI is a number calculated from a person's weight and height and is an inexpensive and easy-to-perform method of screening for weight categories (Barnes & Schoenborn, 2012).

Assumptions

The following assumptions were made for this study:

1. That all participants would respond truthfully and to the best of their knowledge, according to the instructions provided;
2. That the sample of research participants would be representative of individuals who exercised with or without a coach so that the study results would have a reasonable degree of generalization in a similar population;
3. That the instruments of measurement were reliable and valid indicators of the constructs studied; and

4. That the data were accurately recorded and accurately analyzed.

Limitations

The sampling technique for the study was not random. A convenience sample was used by the researcher by selecting participants who were patients in a clinical setting where the researcher worked. A second limitation was that all participants were voluntary. Participants may have felt some pressure to respond in order to be helpful to the researcher. However, because the surveys were not completed in the researcher's presence and were returned in sealed envelopes, the participants did have the option of not completing a survey without this action being known to the researcher. Another limitation was the use of a self-report survey and/or questionnaire. In order to present themselves in a favorable manner, participants may have provided inaccurate responses rather than responses that accurately described their behaviors. Finally, the validity of the study was limited to the reliability of the instruments utilized.

Variables

The study examined whether overweight individuals who exercised regularly used a coach or exercised on their own. The dependent variable was adherence to exercise as defined in the operational definitions. The independent variables were (a) use of a coach, (b) SE, and (c) SE.

Setting

The setting was a family practice medical clinic that accepted most types of insurance as well as Medicare, Medi-Cal, and cash paying patients of all ages. The family practice clinic has three medical doctors and three nurse practitioners. It is situated in a northern California resort town with a year round population of about

23,400 permanent residents, over 70% of whom are Caucasian. Participants in this convenience sample completed the questionnaires either before or after their scheduled medical appointment with the principal researcher while sitting in the exam room or in the waiting room.

Sample

Individual participants were the units of assessment. Participants in the study were patients in a family practice clinic. The sample of the study was a convenience sample of approximately 100 adults who were 18 years of age or older who volunteered to be in the study. In addition, the sample included only participants who were capable of participating in physical activity and was limited to adults who could speak, read, and write English.

Instruments

The three instruments used to gather data for the study were (a) a demographic questionnaire (Appendix A), (b) the short form of the General Self-Efficacy Scale (GSE-6) survey (Appendix B), and (c) the Self-Regulation Questionnaire for Exercise (SRQ-E; Appendix C). Included with these three instruments were a script for invitation to participate in a research study (Appendix D), consent to participate in a research study (Appendix E), and survey instructions (Appendix F).

Demographic Questionnaire

The demographic questionnaire (Appendix A) is an eight-item, self-report questionnaire that contains questions related to gender, age, weight and height, ethnicity, marital status, number of days per week participating in an exercise program, and whether or not an exercise coach was used.

General Self-Efficacy Scale Survey

The GSE-6 survey (Appendix B), adapted from Bandura's SE theory (Romppel et al., 2013) uses a Likert scale and contains eight questions that are used to assess the sense of personal competence that participants feel in order to deal effectively with a variety of situations.

SRQ-E

The SRQ-E (Appendix C) utilizes a 12-question Likert-scale survey to measure the variety of reasons why participants do or do not exercise.

Data Collection Procedure

Permission to proceed with this study was obtained from the Institutional Review Board (IRB) of California State University, Long Beach (CSULB). Approval was granted on October 24, 2013; the study commenced on October 25, 2013, and continued through February 20, 2014.

All patients who fit the criteria were read a script describing the study. After verbal consent was obtained, they were handed an envelope packet that contained the survey instructions (Appendix F), a demographic questionnaire (Appendix A), the GSE-6 survey (Appendix B), and, SRQ-E (Appendix C). The participants completed the study packet either before or after their medical appointment and handed the data back to the principal investigator in the sealed envelope. The researcher and no other clinical staff were in the exam or waiting area while the participant completed the surveys. Research packets were stored in a locked drawer at the principal investigator's desk and transferred at the end of each day to a locked file cabinet in the home office of the principal investigator.

Protection of Human Subjects

In order to maintain the protection of participants' rights and to confirm that the research was to be carried out in an ethical manner, the researcher's committee members and the IRB of CSULB reviewed the research proposal. No participant's signature, name, address, telephone number, or other unique identifiers were noted on the survey material in order to safeguard the anonymity of participants. Prior to collection of study materials, all participants were informed of the purpose of the study, the risks and benefits of participation in the study, and the rights of research participants. The participants also were informed that their participation in the study was voluntary, that they were not required to answer any question that they did not choose to answer, and that they could withdraw from the study at any time. The care that they were to receive that day or any day in the study setting, a medical clinic, would not be in any way affected by their choice to participate or not to participate in the study. All information that might identify a participant will not be disclosed except with the participant's permission and will otherwise remain confidential. All data from the study will be kept in a locked file cabinet in the researcher's home for 3 years and then will be shredded. Only the researcher, the Doctorate of Nursing Practice (DNP) committee, and statisticians were exclusively allowed access to raw data from the study.

Data Analysis

The Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS®), Version 20, was used to perform analysis of the data in this study. Both descriptive and correlational statistics were used in this study to analyze collected data.

RESULTS

This chapter presents the results of the data analysis conducted to address the primary and two-part secondary research questions. The first research question explored the relationship of adherence to exercise in overweight individuals who used a health coach. The two-part second research question was regarding the relationship of SE and self-regulation on adherence to exercise.

This chapter is divided into three major sections. In the first section, descriptive statistics provide an overview of the demographics of the sample including age, BMI, gender, ethnicity, marital status, exercise frequency, and use of a healthcare coach for exercise. The two-part second section reports the relationship of self-efficacy to exercise adherence and the relationship of self-regulation to exercise adherence.

Descriptive Statistics

The total sample size was comprised of 76 participants (see Table 1); 100 surveys were collected, but 24 were not completed correctly or were returned uncompleted and therefore were excluded.

Table 1

Descriptive Statistics Regarding Study Participants (N = 76)

Factor	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	SD
Age	19	84	50.45	15.023
Height	52	76	67.28	4.170
Weight	109	350	179.53	47.313
Body Mass Index	14.97	48.08	27.93	6.960

Study participants ranged from 19 to 84 years of age, with a mean age of 50.47 (see Figure 2).

Figure 2. Age distribution of study participants.

The mean for height of participants was 67.28 inches with a minimum of 52 inches and a maximum of 76 inches (see Figure 3).

Figure 3. Height of study participants (inches).

With respect to weight, the mean was 179.53 pounds, with a maximum of 350 pounds and a minimum 109 pounds. The distribution was skewed to the left, as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Weight of study participants (pounds).

Using the height and weigh data collected, the BMI was calculated. The mean BMI was 27.93, with a minimum of 14.47 and maximum of 48.08 (see Figure 5). Sixty-four percent of the participants were overweight.

Figure 5. Body Mass Index of study participants.

The gender distribution of all study participants was represented by more females than males with 43 female and 33 male participants (see Table 2).

Table 2

Gender Distribution of Study Participants

Gender	<i>f</i>	%	Valid %
Female	43	56.6	56.6
Male	<u>33</u>	<u>43.4</u>	<u>43.4</u>
Total	76	100.0	100.0

The ethnicity of participants was primarily White-Caucasian individuals (86.8%). The second highest ethnic group represented was Hispanic-Latino (see Figure 6).

Figure 6. Ethnic distribution of study participants.

Regarding marital status, 56.6% of the participants were married and 18.4% were single (see Figure 7).

Figure 7. Marital status of study participants.

It was found that almost a third of participants (31.6%) exercised 1–2 days a week; 28.9% exercised 3–4 days a week. Nearly 8% (7.9%) exercised every day, and 10.5% did not exercise at all (see Figure 8).

Figure 8. Participants' exercise days per week.

It was found that eight participants used an exercise health coach and 68 did not (see Table 3). Only one overweight participant exercised with a coach (see Table 4). In this study, most of those who were exercising with an exercise health coach were women (see Table 5).

Correlational Statistics

Exercise Adherence by Overweight Individuals Using a Coach

The primary research question in this study was to determine whether there was a positive effect on exercise adherence for overweight individuals who utilized an exercise health coach. There were not enough data on overweight individuals who utilized a health exercise coach based on the sample utilized. Out of the 76 participants, there was only one overweight individual who used an exercise health coach. This situation resulted in a high p value (.82) for the positive trend test (Cochran-Armitage trend test); therefore, there was not enough evidence to conclude a positive effect on exercise adherence for overweight individuals who utilized an exercise health coach (see Table 6).

Self-Efficacy, Self-Regulation, and Exercise Adherence

The two-part secondary research question was to determine (a) whether there was a relationship between SE and exercise adherence in overweight and normal-weight individuals who exercised and (b) whether there was a relationship between SR and exercise adherence in overweight and normal-weight individuals who exercised. Exercise adherence was defined as participation in 20 minutes or more of exercise 3 or more days a week.

Table 3

Use of Exercise Health Coach by Study Participants

Use of coach	<i>f</i>	%	Valid %
No	68	89.5	89.5
Yes	<u>8</u>	<u>10.5</u>	<u>10.5</u>
Total	76	100.0	100.0

Table 4

Cross-tabulation: Overweight Participants With Coach

Coach	Overweight	Obesity	Total
No	20	48	68
Yes	<u>7</u>	<u>1</u>	<u>8</u>
Total	27	49	76

Table 5

Cross-tabulation: Gender of Participants With Coach

Gender	Overweight	Obesity	Total
Female	20	23	43
Male	<u>7</u>	<u>26</u>	<u>33</u>
Total	27	49	76

Table 6

Participants' Frequency of Exercise With Coach (N = 76)

Coach	Days of exercise per week					Total
	0	1	2	3	4	
No	7	16	12	9	4	48
Yes	<u>0</u>	<u>0</u>	<u>1</u>	<u>0</u>	<u>0</u>	<u>1</u>
Total	7	17	13	9		49

To assess SR and SE with respect to exercise adherence, the scores of the two surveys, the GSE-6 and the SRQ-E, were averaged. This was done by calculating the mean of all 12 SR questions and the mean of all eight SE questions for overweight and normal-weight individuals.

The Poisson regression model was used for the frequency of exercise and SE scores. From the analyzed data, it was determined that the relationship between SE and exercise adherence was not significant ($p = .75$).

Again, the Poisson regression model was used for frequency of exercise and SR scores. It was determined, based on the analyzed data, that the relationship between SR and adherence was significant ($p = .004$).

Alternatively, to test the relationship between exercise adherence and SR, an independent t test was performed (see Table 7). There was a statistically significant difference in SR self-regulation between those who had exercise adherence and those who did not ($t = -3.393$, $p = .001$). The mean difference for the sample of the two groups was -10.36648, which meant that those who exercised at least 3 times a week

had an average total SR score that was 10.36648 larger than the average total SR of those who exercised less than 3 days a week in this sample. Those who had exercise adherence had significantly more SR than those who did not.

Table 7

Independent t Test: Self-Regulation (SR), Self-Efficacy (SE), and Exercise Adherence

Factor	Mean difference	SE difference	df	t	p
Total SR	-10.36648	3.05525	74	-3.393	.001
Total SE	- 2.05114	1.63995	74	-1.251	.215

Similarly, an independent *t* test was conducted to test the relationship between SE and exercise adherence (see Table 7). The test confirmed that there was no statistically significant difference in SE between those who had exercise adherence compared to those who did not have exercise adherence ($t = -1.251, p = .215$).

Summary of Data Analysis

There were not enough data in the study to determine whether or not exercising with a coach had a positive effect on exercise adherence in overweight individuals. The analysis showed a relationship between SR and adhering to an exercise regimen. It showed that SE might not affect overweight individuals' ability to adhere to an exercise regimen; however, it showed it is possible to increase the likelihood of adhering to regular exercise by regulating one's actions.

DISCUSSION

This chapter deals with the findings of the study and draws conclusions from the study findings. In addition, limitations of the study and suggestions for future research are discussed.

The purpose of this study was to examine whether there was a positive effect on overweight individuals who utilized an exercise coach. The secondary purpose was to explore the relationship of SE and SR in exercise adherence. Patients from a family medical clinic completed a demographic questionnaire and two surveys that measured levels of SE and exercise SR.

Research Questions

The primary research question in this study was, “Is there a positive effect on exercise adherence in overweight individuals who utilize an exercise coach?” The secondary research question had two parts:

1. Is there a relationship between SE and exercise adherence in overweight and normal-weight individuals who exercise?
2. Is there a relationship between SR and exercise adherence in overweight and normal-weight individuals who exercise?

Findings and Discussion

Primary Research Question

There were not enough data from the sample collected to determine whether there was a positive effect on exercise adherence in overweight individuals who utilized an exercise coach, as only one participant who used an exercise coach was overweight. This situation resulted in a high p value ($p = .82$) for the positive trend test (Cochran-

Armitage trend test); therefore, there was not a sufficient amount of evidence to conclude whether or not there was a positive effect on exercise adherence in overweight individuals who utilized an exercise coach. Three reasons in particular may have been responsible for this problem. First, the size of the sample was 76 participants; overweight individuals who utilized an exercise coach may have been better represented if there had been a larger sample surveyed. Second, the geographic location of the study was in a small resort town where there were more limited options for an exercise coach than may have been found in a larger community. Third, the participants surveyed were a convenience sample from a family practice clinic, many of whom had multiple comorbidities as well as mental health problems. Including a healthier population in the study may have provided a larger sample of overweight individuals who utilized an exercise coach.

Secondary Research Questions

It was interesting to note that there was not a significant relationship between SE and exercise adherence. The instrument used to determine this was a general SE survey. The results demonstrated that individuals in this survey who had higher levels of SE did not necessarily adhere to an exercise program. The GSE-6 measures efficacy for many types of behaviors and not specifically exercise SE. This issue suggests that an individual may have high SE in other aspects of behavior (e.g., eating healthy, avoiding substance abuse, having monetary success, preserving personal relationships, maintaining career goals or educational goals) but not necessarily have high efficacy in adherence to regular exercise. In addition, the mean age of the participants was 50.45, which could have been a factor in low SE and exercise adherence. Many individuals are

set in their beliefs regarding exercise by the time they have reached middle-age.

Utilizing a larger proportion of younger adults may have yielded different results.

A significant relationship between SR and exercise adherence was found. The survey utilized in this study was specifically related to exercise SR. These findings suggest that those who adhere to a regular exercise program are strong self-regulators in this aspect of their behavior. The findings further suggest that coaching self-regulatory skills may improve adherence to regular exercise. Utilization of an exercise coach to sustain and reinforce SR of exercise may help overweight individuals with poor self-regulatory skills adhere to exercise. It could lead to increased SR in other aspects of their behavior, such as making healthy food choices. This would be an interesting and important behavior change to study. This study may have been limited by using a SR survey specific to exercise instead of a general SR survey, and research would have been enhanced by using both types of surveys.

Implications

The findings of this study have several important practice implications for APNs and healthcare providers in general. First, SR is strongly related to adherence to a regular exercise program. It has already been demonstrated that health coaches have a positive effect on the health of patients with diabetes, CHF, and COPD. Implementing a health coach to enhance self-regulatory behavior in overweight individuals would improve their adherence to regular exercise. Second, this improved SR may be applied to other behaviors, such as better food choices. These better health behaviors lead to healthier individuals with less comorbidity, including increased pain management,

better control of other chronic diseases, and more resistance to acute illness such as influenza.

Limitations

There are several limitations that warrant recognition in this study. Three factors in particular may have limited the findings in regard to the primary research question:

1. The size of the sample was 76 participants. Overweight individuals who utilized an exercise coach may have been better represented if there had been a larger sample surveyed.
2. The geographic location of the study was in a small resort town where there could have been more limited options for an exercise coach than may have been found in a larger community.
3. The participants surveyed were a convenience sample from a family practice clinic, many of whom had multiple comorbidities as well as mental health problems. Including a healthier population in the study may have provided a larger sample of overweight individuals who utilized an exercise coach.

There were limitations also in regard to the study's secondary research questions. The GSE measures efficacy for many types of behaviors and not specifically exercise SE. This factor may have been a limitation to the study because exercise SE specifically was not examined. Many individuals with high SE in some behaviors do not have high SE in exercise adherence or other healthy behaviors.

This study may have been limited by using a SR survey specific to exercise instead of a general SR survey or, alternatively, utilizing both the exercise SR survey and a general SR survey.

Suggestions for Future Research

Obesity is prevalent in all communities across the United States, as is the lack of exercise adherence at a beneficial level. This study examined some of the behaviors that might promote better exercise adherence and lead to better health. It emphasizes the need for economically feasible and practical interventions that have been proven to promote healthier behaviors in patients with other chronic conditions. These findings could be generalized to include use of the health coach in the clinical setting for promoting exercise.

Future research that introduces a health coach for improving exercise adherence in overweight individuals would be very enlightening. This intervention could prove to be cost saving and to assist the primary care provider in desperately needed close follow-up and coaching of this group of patients. In addition, the intervention could free up the primary care provider to provide other care and thus decrease the burden on the healthcare system. Implementation of a health coach in the clinical setting could be modeled after programs already in place for COPD, CHF and diabetes. Coaches would have to be skilled in teaching and encouraging self-regulatory processes.

Another study may want to examine a healthier sample or utilize a randomized study that obtains healthier participants outside of the clinical setting as well as participants in the clinical setting. Both specific and general scales for SE and SR could be used.

This study is important because it contributes to the body of nursing knowledge regarding promotion of healthy lifestyles and reducing obesity. It opens the door for

more research and perhaps implementation of the patient coach as an exercise coach for obese and overweight individuals.

REFERENCES

- Ashford, J. B., & LeCroy, C. W. (2010). *Human behavior in the social environment: A multidimensional perspective* (4th ed.). Belmont, CA: Wadsworth Cengage Learning.
- Ashford, S., Edmunds, J., & French, D. P. (2010). What is the best way to change self-efficacy to promote lifestyle and recreational physical activity? A systematic review with meta-analysis. *British Journal of Health Psychology, 15*, 265–288.
- Ashworth, N. L., Chad, K. E., Harrison, E. L., Reeder, B. A., & Marshall, S. C. (2005). Home versus center based physical activity programs in older adults. *Cochrane Musculoskeletal Group*. Retrieved from <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD004017.pub2>
- Bandura, A. (1977). Self-efficacy: Toward a unifying theory of behavioral change. *Psychological Review, 84*, 191–215. Retrieved from <https://wikispaces.psu.edu>
- Bandura, A. (1986). The explanatory and predictive scope of self-efficacy theory. *Clinical Social Psychology, 4*, 359–373.
- Bandura, A. (1997). *Self-efficacy: The exercise of control*. New York, NY: Freeman.
- Barnes, P. M., & Schoenborn, C. A. (2012). *Trends in adults receiving a recommendation for exercise or other physical activity from a physician or other health professional* (NCHS Data Brief No. 86). Retrieved from <http://www.cdc.gov/nchs/data/databriefs/db86.pdf>
- Bonakdar, R. A., Christo, P. J., & Clark, M. R. (2013). Obesity-related pain: Time for a new approach that targets systemic inflammation. *Journal of Family Practice, 62*(9), S22–S28.
- Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. (2012). *Overweight and obesity*. Retrieved from <http://www.cdc.gov/obesity/data/index.html>
- Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. (2014, February 15). 2013–2014 influenza season week 7 ending February 14, 2014. *FluView*. Retrieved from <http://www.cdc.gov/flu/weekly>
- Coday, M., Boutin-Foster, C., Goldman Sher, T., Tennant, J., Greaney, M. L., Saunders, S. D., & Somes, G. W. (2005). Strategies for retaining study participants in behavioral intervention trials: Retention experiences of the NIH Behavior Change Consortium. *Annals of Behavioral Medicine, 29*, 55–65.

- DiLillo, V., Siegfried, N. J., & West, D. S. (2003). Incorporating motivational interviewing into behavior obesity treatment. *Cognitive and Behavioral Practice, 10*, 120–130.
- Duncan, I., Beatty, B., & Day, B. (2011). A risk-based evaluation methodology for cost effectiveness of chronic condition health management programs. *North American Actuarial Journal, 15*(1), 1–12.
- Finkelstein, E., Fiebelkorn, I., & Wang, G. (2004). State-level estimates of annual medical expenditures attributed to obesity. *Obesity Research, 12*(1), 18–24.
- Flegal, K., Kit, B., & Graubard, B. (2013). Overweight, obesity, and all-cause mortality—reply. *Journal of the American Medical Association, 309*, 1681–1682.
- Gagne, M., & Deci, E. L. (2005). Self-determination theory and work motivation. *Journal of Organizational Behavior, 26*, 331–362.
- Haskell, W. L., Lee, I., Pate, R. R., Powell, K. E., Blair, S. N., Franklin, B. A., . . . Bauman, A. (2007). Physical activity and public health: Updated recommendations for adults from the American College of Sports Medicine and the American Heart Association. *Medicine and Science in Sports and Exercise, 116*, 1423–1434.
- Hayes, E., & Kalmakis, K. A. (2007). From the sidelines: Coaching as a nurse practitioner strategy for improving health outcomes. *Journal of the American Academy of Nurse Practitioners, 19*, 555–562.
- Hayes, E., McCahon, C., Panahi, M. R., Hamre, T., & Pohlman, K. (2008). Alliance not compliance: Coaching strategies to improve type 2 diabetes outcomes. *Journal of the American Academy of Nurse Practitioners, 20*, 155–162.
- Kilgore, M. D. (2010). Transitional case management: A method for establishing self-advocacy and reducing hospital readmissions in COPD patients. *Home Health Care Management and Practice, 22*, 435–438.
- Lanese, B. S., Dey, A., Srivastava, P., & Figler, R. (2011a). Introducing the health coach at a primary care practice: Impact on quality and cost (Part 1). *Hospital Topics, 89*(1), 16–22.
- Lanese, B. S., Dey, A., Srivastava, P., & Figler, R. (2011b). Introducing the health coach at a primary care practice: A pilot study (Part 2). *Hospital Topics, 89*(2), 37–42.

- Lee, L. L., Arthur, A., & Avis, M. (2008). Using self-efficacy theory to develop interventions that help older people overcome psychological barriers to physical activity: A discussion paper. *International Journal of Nursing Studies, 45*, 1690–1699.
- Lentz, E. R. (2002). *Self-efficacy in nursing: Research and measurement perspectives*. New York, NY: Springer.
- Markland, D. (2000). *Behavioral Regulation in Exercise Questionnaire (BREQ-2)*. Retrieved from http://pages.bangor.ac.uk/~pes004/exercise_motivation/downloads/breq2.pdf
- McAuley, E., Mullen, S. P., Szabo, A. N., White, S. M., Wojcicki, T. R., Mailey, E. L., . . . Kramer, A. F. (2011). Self-regulatory processes and exercise adherence in older adults: Executive function and self-efficacy effects. *American Journal of Preventative Medicine, 41*, 284–290.
- Mceachan, R. C., Sutton, S., & Myers, L. B. (2010). Mediation of personality influences on physical activity within the theory of planned behavior. *Journal of Health Psychology, 15*, 1170–1180.
- Moran, K., Burson, R., & Conrad, D. (2014). *The doctor of nursing practice scholarly project*. Burlington, MA: Jones & Bartlett Learning.
- Mullen, S. P., Wojeiki, T. R., Mailey, E. L., Szabo, A. N., Gothe, N. P., Olson, E. A., . . . McAuley, E. (2013). A profile for predicting attrition from exercise in older adults. *Preventative Science, 14*, 489–496.
- National Institute of Health, National Institute of Diabetes and Digestive and Kidney Diseases, Weight-Control Information Network. (2013). *Overweight and obesity statistics*. Retrieved from <http://win.niddk.nih.gov/statistics/>
- National Organization of Nurse Practitioners. (2013, April). *Advanced practice nurse (APN) as health and wellness coach: Teaching APN students to transform healthcare* [Pamphlet]. Handout at 39th annual meeting, Pittsburgh, PA.
- Newnham-Kanas, C., Irwin, J. D., & Morrow, D. (2008). Co-active life coaching as a treatment for adults with obesity. *International Journal of Evidence Based Coaching and Mentoring, 6*(2), 1–12.
- Newnham-Kanas, C. N., Irwin, J. D., Morrow, D., & Battram, D. (2011). The quantitative assessment of motivational interviewing using co-active life coaching skills as an intervention for adults struggling with obesity. *International Coaching Psychology Review, 6*, 211–228.

- Oaten, M., & Cheng, K. (2006). Longitudinal gains in self-regulation from regular physical exercise. *British Journal of Health Psychology, 11*, 717–733.
- Ogden, C. L., Carroll, M. D., Kit, B. K., & Flegal, K. M. (2012). *Prevalence of obesity in the United States, 2009–2012* (NCHS Data Brief No. 82). Retrieved from <http://www.cdc.gov/nchs/data/databriefs/db82.pdf>
- Pearson, E. S., Irwin, J. D., Morrow, D., & Hall, C. R. (2012). The CHANGE program: Comparing an interactive versus prescriptive obesity intervention on university students' self-esteem and quality of life. *Applied Psychology: Health and Well-Being, 4*, 369–389.
- Rodgers, W. M., Hall, C. R., Duncan, L. R., Pearson, E., & Milne, M. I. (2010). Becoming a regular exerciser: Examining change in behavioral regulations among exercise initiates. *Psychology of Sport and Exercise, 11*, 378–386.
- Romppel, M., Hermann-Lingen, C., Wachter, R., Edelmann, F., Dungen, H., Pieske, B., & Grande, G. (2013). A short form of the general self-efficacy scale (GSE-6): Development, psychometric properties and validity in an intercultural non-clinical sample and a sample of patients with heart failure. *Psycho-social Medicine, 10*. doi:10.3205/psm000091
- Schelling, S., Munsch, S., Meyer, A. H., Newark, P., Biedert, E., & Margraf, J. (2009). Increasing the motivation for physical activity in obese patients. *International Journal of Eating Disorders, 42*, 130–138.
- Shaw, R., Gillies, M., Barber, J., MacIntyre, K., Harkins, C., Findlay, I., . . . MacIntyre, P. (2012). Pre-exercise screening and health coaching in CHD secondary prevention: a qualitative study of the patient experience. *Health Education Research, 27*, 424–436.
- U.S. Department of Health and Human Services. (2014). *Key features of the Affordable Care Act*. Retrieved from <http://www.hhs.gov/healthcare/facts/timeline/index.html>
- Wadden, T. A., Butryn, M. L., & Wilson, C. (2007). Lifestyle modification for the management of obesity. *Gastroenterology, 132*, 2226–2238.
- West, D. D., Gorkin, A. A., Subak, L. L., Foster, G., Bragg, C., Hecht, J., . . . Wing, R. R. (2011). A motivation-focused weight loss maintenance program is an effective alternative to a skill-based approach. *International Journal of Obesity, 35*, 259–269.
- Williams, D. M. (2010). Outcome expectancy and self-efficacy: Theoretical implications of an unresolved contradiction. *Personality and Social Psychology Review, 14*, 417–425.

- Williams, S. L., & French, D. P. (2011). What are the most effective intervention techniques for changing physical activity self-efficacy and physical activity behavior—and are they the same? *Health Education Research, 26*, 308–322.
- Williams, S. R. (1994). *Essentials of nutrition and diet therapy* (6th ed.). St. Louis, MO: Mosby-Year Book.
- Wilson, P. M., Mack, D. E., & Grattan, K. P. (2008). Understanding motivation for exercise: A self-determination theory perspective. *Canadian Psychology, 49*, 250–256.
- Wilson, P. M., Sabiston, C. M., Mack, D. E., & Blanchard, C. M. (2012). On the nature and function of scoring protocols used in exercise motivation research: An empirical study of the behavior regulation in exercise questionnaire. *Psychology of Sport and Exercise, 13*, 614–622.
- World Health Organization. (2013). *10 facts on obesity*. Retrieved from <http://www.who.int/features/obesity/en>

APPENDIX A**DEMOGRAPHICS QUESTIONNAIRE**

1. What is your gender?
 - Male
 - Female

2. How old are you? Please write your age in years.
_____ years old

3. What is the ethnic background you identify with most? Check only one.
 - Native American
 - Asian
 - Black/African American
 - Hispanic/Latino
 - Middle Eastern
 - Pacific Islander
 - White/Caucasian
 - Indian/Eastern Asian

4. What is your marital status?
 - Single (never been married)
 - Married
 - Separated
 - Divorced
 - Widowed

5. What is your height in inches?

_____ inches

6. What is your weight in pounds?

_____ pounds

7. How many days a week do you usually participate in an exercise activity?

0

1–2

3–4

5–6

7

8. Are you currently exercising with an exercise coach such as a personal trainer, a group class leader, or an athletic coach?

Yes

No

(Prepared by Barbara L. Pidermann.)

APPENDIX B

GENERAL SELF-EFFICACY SCALE

Please rate the following statements and indicate how true each is for you. Use the following 1–7 scale:

- | | | | | | | | |
|--|-----------------|---|---|---------------|---|---|-----------|
| | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 | 6 | 7 |
| | Not at all true | | | Somewhat true | | | Very true |
-
- ___ 1. I will be able to achieve most of the goals that I have set for myself.
- ___ 2. When facing difficult tasks, I am certain that I will accomplish them.
- ___ 3. In general, I think that I can obtain outcomes that are important to me.
- ___ 4. I believe I can succeed at most any endeavor to which I set my mind.
- ___ 5. I will be able to successfully overcome many challenges.
- ___ 6. I am confident that I can perform effectively on many different tasks.
- ___ 7. Compared to other people, I can do most tasks very well.
- ___ 8. Even when things are tough, I can perform quite well.

(Taken from “A Short Form of the General Self-Efficacy Scale (GSE-6): Development, Psychometric Properties and Validity in an Intercultural Non-clinical Sample and a Sample of Patients With Heart Failure,” by M. Romppel, C. Hermann-Lingen, R. Wachter, F. Edelmann, H. Dungen, B. Pieske, and G. Grande, 2013, *Psycho-social Medicine*, 10, p. 43, doi:10.3205/psm000091)

APPENDIX C

SRQ-E

There are a variety of reasons why people exercise. Please indicate how true each these reasons is for why you exercise. Use the following 1–7 scale:

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Not at all true			Somewhat true			Very true

Why do you exercise?

- ___ 1. Because I simply enjoy exercising.
- ___ 2. Because exercising is important and beneficial for my health and lifestyle.
- ___ 3. Because I would feel bad about myself if I didn't do it.
- ___ 4. Because it is fun and interesting.
- ___ 5. Because others like me better when I am in shape.
- ___ 6. Because I'd be afraid of falling too far out of shape.
- ___ 7. Because it helps my image.
- ___ 8. Because it is personally important to me to exercise.
- ___ 9. Because I feel pressured to exercise.
- ___ 10. Because I have a strong value for being active and healthy.
- ___ 11. For the pleasure of discovering and mastering new training techniques.
- ___ 12. Because I want others to see me as physically fit.

(Adapted from *Behavioral Regulation in Exercise Questionnaire (BREQ-2)*, by D. Markland, 2000, retrieved from http://pages.bangor.ac.uk/~pes004/exercise_motivation/downloads/breq2.pdf.)

APPENDIX D**SCRIPT FOR INVITATION TO PARTICIPATE IN RESEARCH STUDY**

Hello, [patient's name], my name is Barbara Pidermann. I am currently a Doctorate of Nursing Practice student from the California State University consortium program associated with the School of Nursing at California State University, Long Beach. I am conducting a research study and have selected you to participate because you fit the criteria for the study.

The purpose of the study is to determine the relationships of certain characteristics that motivate patients who are obese or overweight to adhere to a regular exercise program.

The three short surveys utilized in this study consist of eight (8) demographic questions, eight (8) questions about general motivation, and twelve (12) about exercise motivation. The entire study should take 10–15 minutes.

Are you interested in volunteering to participate in this study today?

(Prepared by Barbara L. Pidermann.)

APPENDIX E

CONSENT TO PARTICIPATE IN RESEARCH STUDY

The Study

Title of the Study: A Study to Examine Self-Efficacy, Self-Regulation and Their Relationship to Overweight Patients Who Utilize a Health Coach.

My name is Barbara Pidermann. I am a practicing Family Nurse Practitioner and a Doctorate of Nursing Practice (DNP) student from the California State University Consortium program associated with the School of Nursing at California State University, Long Beach. You are being asked to participate in a research study conducted by myself under the direction of Dr. David E. Kumrow, Associate Professor in the School of Nursing at California State University, Long Beach.

You have been selected as a possible participant in this study because you are (1) 18 years of age or older, (2) able to speak, read, and write English, (3) fit the criteria for body mass index, and (4) are able to exercise for at least 30 minutes total a day.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study is to establish whether there is a positive effect on exercise adherence in overweight patients who use a health coach. This will be determined by exploring the relationship of self-efficacy and self-regulation in overweight patients who exercise with and without a health coach.

Procedures

Your participation in this study is voluntary. If you choose to participate, please fill out this survey which consists of eight (8) demographic questions, eight (8) questions about general motivation, and twelve (12) about exercise motivation. The entire study should take 10–15 minutes.

Potential Risks

There is minimal risk associated with self-report questionnaires. However, there may be potential risk for mild anxiety when recalling information.

Potential Benefits to Participants

There will be no specific benefits to individual participants predicted immediately from the research study. This study is important in that it contributes to the scientific knowledge base in the field of advanced practice nursing and promotes potential improvement of healthy lifestyle. Results of this study may have the potential to improve health care delivery for overweight patients.

Payment for Participation

There is no financial benefit for participation in the study.

Confidentiality

No personal individual identifier(s) will be collected as part of this research study. Participant identity and survey responses will remain anonymous, and confidentiality will be maintained as required by law. Demographic questions will be limited to gender, age, ethnicity, marital status, weight, height, amount, if any of exercise, and use of coaching. Only group statistics will be reported. Only the researchers will have access to raw data. The surveys will be stored in a locked filing cabinet in the researcher's home for a period of three years after the completion of the study and will then be shredded.

Rights of Research Subjects, Participants, and Withdrawal

Your participation in this study is voluntary. You may withdraw from participation at any time without consequence. Participation or non-participation does not affect your care in this medical facility or other personal rights. You may choose to leave certain questions blank during the survey, if you feel uncomfortable in responding, yet remain in the study.

If you have questions regarding your rights as a research participant please contact:
The Office of Research, CSULB
1250 Bellflower Blvd., Long Beach, CA 90840
University Phone: (562) 985-5314
University E-mail: research@csulb.edu

Advisor/Faculty Supervisor of Student Research Project
If you have questions regarding this study, please contact:
Barbara Pidermann, MSN, FNP, Principal Researcher at (xxx) xxx-xxxx or
David Kumrow, Ed.D., Assistant Professor, CSULB
University Phone: (562) 985-8082
Faculty E-mail: David.Kumrow@csulb.edu

APPENDIX F

SURVEY INSTRUCTIONS

The research study consists of 3 parts:

1. An eight (8) question demographic survey. It is important that you answer each demographic question accurately. Select only one answer for each question.

Example: Place an “X” in the bubble by your answer or if indicated write in the requested information.

1. What is your gender? Place an “X” next to your choice.

Male

Female

2. What is your height in inches?

69 inches

2. An eight (8) question general self-efficacy survey. It is important that you answer each question as closely as it applies to you at this time. Select only one answer for each question. Write one number only for each response and place the number next to the statement. Use the following 1–7 scale:

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Not at all true			Somewhat true			Very true

Example

- 2 1. I can always manage to solve difficult problems if I try hard enough.

3. A twelve (12) question self-regulation for exercise survey. There are a variety of reasons why people exercise. Please indicate how true each of these reasons is for why you exercise. Write one number only for each response and place the number next to the statement. Use the following 1–7 scale:

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Not at all true			Somewhat true			Very true

Example

Why do you exercise?

5 1. Because I simply enjoy exercising.

(Prepared by Barbara L. Pidermann.)